

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

COMMERCIALIZATION AS A DETERMINING FACTOR OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE NATIONAL INNOVATION SYSTEM OF THE REPUBLIC OF KAZAKHSTAN

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Abstract

This article is dedicated to the current issues of the development of the national economy of the Republic of Kazakhstan. It addresses the matters concerning the formation of innovative directions associated with the commercialization of innovations within the context of prospective directions of state policy. Through the examination of this thematic area, which is based on the influence of novelties in the economic policy process, pathways for further shaping contemporary transformations affecting the competitiveness of the state have been delineated.

Keywords: *innovation process, innovative activity, commercialization, national economy, national innovation system.*

An essential component of the innovation process is the commercialization of innovations. Commercialization is the outcome of successful innovation activities by enterprises, which have led to the implementation of innovation and the establishment of sustainable financial streams.

The commercialization of innovations implies the achievement of economic benefits from the implementation of scientific and technical developments. It is

also important to note that innovative products may initially have consumer value, meaning they are subject to commercialization, or they may not possess such characteristics (not being a commodity) but may develop them later (2011). Therefore, commercialization represents the ultimate result of the innovation process in entrepreneurship. Commercialization of innovations is commonly understood in several dimensions, as illustrated in Figure 1:

Figure 1. The importance of commercialization of innovations

Commercialization is the process through which a new product or service is introduced into the general market. Commercialization is divided into stages, from the initial appearance of the product to its mass production and deployment. This includes production, distribution, marketing, and sales. The commercialization strategy requires businesses to develop a marketing plan, determine how the product will be brought to the market, and anticipate obstacles on the path to success. Research commercialization provides new products and services that can be used to address some of the most pressing life issues, as well as in various business domains (2008).

The importance of innovation commercialization is evident in practice. According to a survey by McKinsey (2010), only 39% of executives believe their companies are good at commercializing new products. In the same survey, a third of them identified commercializing innovations as one of the main issues, and 43% stated that more significant problems include selecting ideas for advancement. Academic research reflects these concerns. For example, Kyeza and Frattini (2011) argued that many products in high-tech industries fail due to a poor understanding of the commercialization process. However, in the theory and practice of management, there is no clear understanding of how commercialization decisions affect the market failures of new high-tech products. Taken together, this data suggests the need to specify the concept of innovation commercialization.

Previous research linked the ability to successfully commercialize innovations to a company's capabilities, human resource practices, the nature of top management teams, and the external environment in which the company operates (2017). The choice of the form to adopt is determined by the profit earned from commercialization and the company's potential for commercializing innovations. Potential risks of consumer disinterest in innovative products should also be considered (2022).

Modern trends in technology development call for the timely "production" of potentially commercialize knowledge, as it contributes to addressing today's challenges. Enterprises or their structural units must not only study consumer needs, which is one of the main strategic focuses of innovative activities but also be able to optimally organize the commercialization process itself.

The advantages of commercialization are manifold. The commercialization of intellectual property benefits researchers, industrial enterprises, customers, universities, and the government. Successful entry into new markets in a rapidly changing world is facilitated by a focus on continuously reducing product costs and employing an optimal new product development strategy.

In the Republic of Kazakhstan, the existing national economic system is oriented towards the implementation of state programs. One of the entrepreneurial factors is the comprehensive long-term "Kazakhstan-2050" Strategy, which envisions the country's transition to a knowledge-based economy within 10-15 years and inclusion among the world's 30 most developed countries by 2050.

The knowledge economy will ensure growth, diversification, and global competitiveness by improving the quality of the country's key production factors: human capital, infrastructure, and institutions. The Strategy outlines priority areas, including the need to enhance scientific potential. Research funding is planned at three percent of the Gross Domestic Product to increase scientific potential, accelerate the transfer of knowledge and technology through foreign direct investment, and enhance the efficiency of the national innovation system.

The national innovation system is a set of institutions within the public and private sectors of the economy, which independently and interactively create new knowledge, skills, abilities, and results of scientific and design activity, determining the emergence, development, and dissemination of new technologies.

Various aspects of forming and developing national innovation systems in countries with transitional economies are studied by foreign scholars, including the works of authors such as G. Dosi (1982), C. Freeman (1995), H. Odagiri, A. Goto (1993), Ch. Edquist, B.-A. Lundvall (1993), and others.

Kazakhstani scholars have also dedicated research to the current issues of innovation process development and the formation of national innovation systems in countries with transitional economies, including the works of N.A. Barlybayeva (2006), Yu.V. Batalov, E.A. Kolos (2011), K.T. Duysenbayeva (2007), O.S. Sabdena (2011), and others.

The National Innovation System of the Republic of Kazakhstan comprises several components:

Scientific Potential, including:

- State scientific organizations such as national research centers, research institutes, higher educational institutions, and project institutes.

- Scientific organizations within national companies and laboratories at large enterprises.

- Private research and project institutes.

- Small and medium-sized businesses engaged in scientific research.

- Scientific personnel in organizations and individual inventors.

- Material and technical base.

Innovation Entrepreneurship, which performs intermediary functions between the scientific-technical and production sectors. The ultimate goal of innovation entrepreneurship is the development of companies capable of reacting swiftly to current market conditions and establishing mass production of competitive, knowledge-intensive products of a new generation that meet global standards. Innovation entrepreneurship includes:

- Business angels.

- Enterprises.

- Innovation managers.

A Multilevel Innovation Infrastructure, consisting of a complex of interrelated production, consulting, educational, and information structures that serve and provide conditions for innovation activities. The innovation infrastructure comprises elements such as:

- National technology parks.

- Regional technology parks.

- Technology business incubators.

- Science towns, and more.

Financial Infrastructure, ensuring comprehensive financing of scientific, production, and educational processes in the field of innovation and technological development. It is based on a combination of various mechanisms of direct and indirect state support for innovation entrepreneurship and infrastructure. The financial infrastructure includes elements like:

- State development institutions.
- Venture funds.
- Enterprises.
- Individual entrepreneurs.
- Second-tier banks, and others.

The formation of Kazakhstan's National Innovation System occurs in an institutional environment characterized by:

- A high level of development of the research system.
- A lack of interest in production to adopt scientific results.
- Low innovation activity of enterprises.
- Stagnation in the manufacturing industry.
- Underdevelopment of a network of small innovative firms.
- Insufficient development of venture entrepreneurship.
- Underdevelopment of high-tech sectors (2006).

To address these issues, the state stimulates the formation and development of the National Innovation System of the Republic of Kazakhstan through direct and indirect support for innovation activities.

Direct state support for innovation activities is based on selecting priority areas for science and technology development, defining a list of "critical technologies," targeted project financing from the state budget, co-financing projects and programs implemented by non-governmental structures, creating innovation activity infrastructure, and more.

Indirect measures to stimulate innovation activities include using fiscal methods (preferential taxation, accelerated depreciation), regulatory and legal regulation in the field of intellectual property creation, transfer, and protection, as well as creating favorable conditions for the operations of entities involved in the commercialization of scientific knowledge.

The commercialization system involves various elements, ranging from motivation and training to initiatives to support specific commercialization projects, such as innovation centers, incubators, patent agencies, and seed capital funds. In many cases, different stakeholders participate individually or in collaboration. The challenge is to create a situation in which various participants collaborate to achieve the common goal of successful commercialization.

Adapting and effectively utilizing existing global knowledge and practices will be the most economical and rational path for the country's development. This undoubtedly contributes to raising the innovation potential to the level of a critical mass that fosters a culture of innovative competition in all sectors of the economy and society.

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